

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR TRAINING STUDENTS IN ORGANIZING SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

Joraeva G.M.

Teacher of Economics and Pedagogical University

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Abstract. *At present time while the process of self-realization is developing nationwide, the study of pedagogy in general and Uzbek folk pedagogy in particular from a historical point of view acquires important scientific, educational and ideological significance. The reason of that every nation has its place in the world only when it has its own spiritual and spiritual image.*

Keywords: *educational process, physically healthy and mentally mature youth, spiritual and educational work, pedagogical mechanism.*

It is important to suggest that based on the peculiarities of organizing communication centers with innovative and technological ideas in higher educational institutions of our republic, improved software and methodological support for organizing educational processes have been created. At the same time, the development of the processes of professional pedagogical education, the development of a pedagogical mechanism for preparing future specialists for spiritual and educational activities is of particular importance.

Everyone knows that among the scientists of our republic are O. Musurmanova, T. Narbaeva, M. Kuronov, S. Nishanova, N. Joraev, A. Begmatov, G. Makhmudova, B. Shermammedov, R. Gaipnazarov, O. Jamoldinova, K. Riskulova, Z. Salieva, U. Utanov in their research explained the pedagogical foundations of the formation of ideological immunity among young people, making decisions about a healthy lifestyle, and the formation of spiritual culture.

Definitely, this is defined in the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated October 8, 2019 PD-5847 “On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.” All these decrees, first of all, “On improving the organization of spiritual, educational and educational work in the higher education system”, “Involving students in literature, art and sports, in a healthy lifestyle, in which they receive aesthetic development.” The plan of spiritual and educational activities for the formation of a culture of taste and professional ethics, analysis of information, love for the country and attachment to its destiny, self-sacrifice, as well as the implementation of this action plan in all higher educational institutions provides important [2].

It should also be noted that the ongoing spiritual and propaganda activities are provided for in Article 12, the Constitution of the Uzbekistan Republic: “Public life in the Republic of Uzbekistan develops on the basis of the diversity of political institutions, ideologies and opinions. No ideology can establish itself as a state ideology” [1].

Training students for organizing spiritual and educational work in the process of vocational pedagogical education is aimed at solving educational problems, i.e. modern educational paradigms:

- value (axiological) approach, spiritual production as the content of human life;

- active approach as a proven method of activity aimed at creating material and spiritual benefits;

- personal approach – spiritual production is manifested in the image of a specific person.

Training for the organization of spiritual and educational work in the process of vocational pedagogical education, first of all, propaganda of the national idea among young people, instilling in them a sense of respect for state symbols and national values, the content of the reforms has been implemented - it is necessary to strictly adhere to the following pedagogical goals, ensuring the composition and its evolution, coherence and continuity, regarding :

- spirituality as a social category, representing the entire spiritual world of a person as an integral system, is the historical formation and existence of knowledge and skills in the system of social ethics, beliefs and values;

- acceptance by students and youth of existing spiritual values do, know and understand them;

- the formation of healthy thinking in the development of personality, based on the understanding and acceptance that ideology is an integral part of our national spirituality;

- to achieve the effectiveness of the spiritual and educational activities of students and youth, the basis is the introduction of effective propaganda methods aimed at developing ideological immunity, religious tolerance and interethnic harmony among young people, as well as preventing them from falling under the influence of understanding foreign ideas from a pedagogical point of view.

By this way, it is understandable the essence of the concepts of spirituality and enlightenment as a result of studying and analyzing research works, carried out by teachers, psychologists and philosophers, linguists, literary scholars, sociologists, and legal scholars. It became the basis for creating a typology of the pedagogical content of the concept of spirituality and enlightenment in the process of professional pedagogical education.

It is important to mention that based on the concept of training students for organizing spiritual and educational work in the process of vocational pedagogical education, revealing the essence of the term “enlightenment” is an important component of our research work.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word “enlightenment” is defined as follows. Enlightenment – knowledge, science, information, acquaintance. Education is an activity aimed at raising the consciousness and culture of people, based on educational, economic, political, religious and philosophical ideas. Education includes all types and directions of dissemination and improvement of knowledge and culture.

In the research by B. Shermammedov, scientifically substantiates that the idea of national independence, uniting young people for a common goal, becomes a national ideology and serves to ensure stable development in the country. “It is known that the essence of creative ideologies at all times has been inextricably linked with the formation and development of education. The ideas created by our people at different stages of historical periods served as the basis for the formation of educational directions that express such aspects as humanism, patriotism, patriotism. This process includes a large historical period from a scientific and historical point of view and creates the need for the effective use of these technologies in the promotion of spiritual and educational activities.”

The historical roots of spirituality mean that it is inextricably linked with the consciousness and psyche of man, and therefore its ideological roots go back to religious teachings. From that, it

is clear that many ideologies express, to one degree or another, the noble ideas mentioned in divine books such as the Psalms, Torah, Bible and Koran.

The teachings of Confucius and Lao Tzu, which laid the path for the development of the Chinese people, were also based on the views of science and enlightenment. Based on the principle of historicity, Unsurulmaoli Kaykovus, Mahmud Kashgari, Imam Bukhari, Musa Khorezmi, Imam Fazzali, Imam Termizi, Imam Motrudi, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Alisher Navai, Amir created scientific and didactic resources. thinkers like Timur are important in education.

Philosophical, psychological-pedagogical, legal, social approaches to the process of preparing students for the organization of spiritual and educational work in the process of vocational pedagogical education, pedagogical conditions and determination of dependence on mysterious factors that classify the historical and stage-by-stage development of spiritual talents in the process of education from the point of view of principle historicity, their justification from a scientific and pedagogical point of view ensures the purposefulness of their use. In this regard, folk pedagogy and the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers serve as an important resource for preparing students for organizing spiritual and educational work in the process of professional pedagogical education.

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